

Original article

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AI SUPPORT FOR QUALITATIVE RESEARCH: VALIDATION OF DIGITAL TWINS THROUGH A CASE STUDY

ALEKSEJ MIGITKO¹, MINJA MARINOVIĆ², NIKOLA CVETKOVIĆ³, UROŠ ŠOŠEVIĆ⁴

¹ Metropolitan University, Faculty of Economics, Finance and Administration, alex.migitko@gmail.com, 0009-0008-2878-7622

² University of Belgrade, Faculty of Organizational Sciences, Belgrade, minja.marinovic@fon.bg.ac.rs, 0009-0005-4346-0239

³ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Organizational Sciences, Belgrade, nikola.cvetkovic@fon.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0003-1979-0703

⁴ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Organizational Sciences, Belgrade, uros.osevic@fon.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0003-0322-8097

Abstract: *This paper explores the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in the context of academic qualitative research, with the main goal of creating a tool that will serve as an auxiliary tool. Its purpose is to automate the process of collecting, analyzing, and synthesizing research insights. By using an AI system to generate so-called digital twins – entities that accurately represent the respondents' thought patterns – researchers are enabled to gain almost instant insight into the attitudes of the target group through natural language interaction. It is important to emphasize that the tool does not replace the researcher himself, but serves solely as a support in gaining insight, providing advice and suggesting directions for further research based on the data already processed. A preliminary evaluation, conducted on a pilot group of respondents, demonstrated a high level of match between the psychometric characteristics of individuals and their digital twins. The basis of this system is a structured set of analytical clusters that encompass different categories of thoughts and profiles, thus enabling thematically focused analysis and application by experts from different fields. The presented results clearly indicate the significant potential of integrating this approach into contemporary scientific practice, with a special emphasis on research projects that rely on an in-depth understanding of complex qualitative data.*

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence, qualitative analysis, digital twins, scientific research.*